

EFFECT OF PANDEMIC ON TEACHING - LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of pandemic period on teaching- learning process. The sample of the study consisted of 280 teachers of secondary to higher secondary schools of Lucknow city, Uttar Pradesh. Effects on teaching-learning process was studied by survey method. Researcher used a questionnaire in this study. The motive of this study is to know the student engagement, technology acquisition, teaching and learning process and faculty experience towards virtual classrooms during Lockdown due to COVID 19. The purpose of this study was to find out the effectiveness of online classes, students' participation in online teaching and perception of faculties towards online teaching. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant effect of pandemic period on teaching- learning process. Digitalization of education and online teaching is not much effective in compare to off line teachers. All respondents admitted that off-line teaching is much more effective than online teaching because in online teaching the teachers and students faced many problems.

Keywords : Pandemic Period, teaching-learning Process.

INTRODUCTION

Pandemic is a disease that spreads across countries or continents. In present time Covid-19 has affected all people in different ways. This pandemic has led to a drastic loss of human life worldwide and presents an unprecedented challenge to education,

public health, food systems and the world of work (WHO, 2020). No one could have predicted that a virus like Covid-19 would come and it will alter the lifestyle of people. Due to covid-19 many changes came to our world and it took sometime for everyone to adopt the new normal life. In this pandemic period, every school & college and other educational institutions were closed to reduce the impact of Covid-19. Though schools were closed, students were attending their classes through various educational initiatives like online classroom etc. Many students faced difficulties to obtain the gadget to attend online classes. Teachers who were experts in classroom teaching were really new to this digital teaching and faced a lot of problems. Students who didn't have own resources to attend the online classes also suffered a lot. In this pandemic period, educated parents were supporting their children in their study but illiterate parents were helpless to support their children.

Variables :

Pandemic : The Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) defines a pandemic as a disease outbreak that has spread across multiple countries and continents and usually impacts many people. The classification of “pandemic” comes when a disease affects the global population. Pandemics are usually caused by new infectious agents (bacteria or viruses) that spread quickly.

Teaching - Learning Process: Combined processes where an educator assesses learning needs, establishes specific learning objectives, develops teaching and learning strategies, implements plan of work and evaluates the outcomes of the instruction.

Objectives of the Study

- To study student's participation in online Classes.

- To study which gadget was mostly used for online classes.
- To study the experience of online platform.
- To study home environment for e-teaching.
- To study the effectiveness of e-learning.

Research Question:

- How many students participated in online classroom?
- Which gadgets were mostly used for online teaching?
- What is the experience of online Platform?
- Did the home environment motivate the students for e-teaching?
- Was e-Learning effective for the students ?

Population:

The population of the study comprised of secondary to senior secondary school teachers of Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh.

Sample Size & Sampling Technique:

The present study was conducted on 280 teachers of secondary to senior secondary school of Lucknow by purposive sampling technique.

Methodology of Study:

The researcher adopted survey method.

Research Tool:

Researcher used self-made questionnaire for survey. Total 280 responses were recorded on Google form.

Testing of Research Questions:

RQ1. The key findings of the study against the research question

'How many students participated in online Classroom?' are as follows:

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the percentage of students participated in online Classroom

The finding of the study indicated that out of 280 teachers, 112 (40%) teachers responded that only 75% students participated in online classroom whereas 87 (31.1%) teachers said that 50% students, 42 (15%) teachers said that 100% and 39 (13.9%) teachers responded that only 25% students participated in online classroom.

RQ2. The key findings of the study against the research question 'Which gadgets were mostly used for online teaching?' are as follows

